

84, in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Seedlings were transplanted at 1/hill, 20- × 20 cm spacing. Fertilizer was 80-40-0 kg NPK/ha.

All mutant lines were 24-26% shorter than Basmati 370 (see table), but panicle

length and 1,000-grain weight were significantly inferior. Mutant strains were similar in grains per panicle and panicle fertility. Their yield potential was 25-51% higher than that of Basmati 370. The attribute of mutant lines that may enhance yield potential seems to be

higher number of productive tillers per plant.

All the mutants exhibited semidwarf plant posture along with higher yielding capability, and may be used directly and indirectly as new gene sources for short culm for Basmati rices. □

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Effect of sclerotia size of *Rhizoctonia solani* on infectivity on rice plants

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Sclerotia of *R. solani*, the causal organism of rice sheath blight (ShB), are produced in large numbers on infected plants and often drop to the soil after harvest. Because they can survive for a long time, they tend to accumulate in the soil and are a primary source of inoculum. We examined sclerotia size and distribution in a naturally infested field and the effect of sclerotia size and number on infectivity of rice plants.

Surface soil from a ShB-infested ricefield was collected after harvest and processed in the laboratory. The sclerotia recovered were measured and grouped by size. The effect of sclerotia size and number on infectivity was tested by inoculating detached rice leaves and rice seedlings with different size and numbers of sclerotia recovered from soil or grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA). Sclerotia produced naturally, sizes 1 × 1, 1.5 × 1.5, 1.8 ×

Table 1. Effect of *R. solani* sclerotia size on infectivity on detached rice leaves.^a IIRRI, 1985.

Sclerotia size ^b (mm)	Lesions ^c (no.)	Lesion sized (mm)
2 × 2	5.1	19 × 5.6
1.8 × 1.8	4.3	17 × 4.5
1.5 × 1.5	2.8	13 × 4.1
1 × 1	1.2	9 × 4

^aData collected 4 d after inoculation. ^bSclerotia recovered from naturally infested soil. ^cNumber counted on each leaf blade inoculated: 2 replications with 10 blades each. ^dAv size lesion measured.

Table 2. Effect of *R. solani* sclerotia size and number on infectivity on rice plants^a in the greenhouse. IIRRI, 1985.

Number inoculated	Lesion length (mm)	Lesion number
<i>0.7 × 0.7 mm</i>		
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0
4	9.5	2.9
5	10.4	5.2
<i>1 × 1 mm</i>		
1	10.5	4.3
2	11.4	5.1
3	14.0	8.2
4	15.2	11.8
5	16.5	13.6
<i>1.5 × 1.5 mm</i>		
1	17.8	12.4
2	19.2	14.9
3	20.2	16.3
4	20.6	17.0
5	20.7	17.4
<i>2 × 2 mm</i>		
1	20.6	10.3
2	21.1	14.5
3	22.0	22.5
4	22.2	28.4
5	23.7	31.6

^aRice cultivar IR36. Disease scoring 5 d after inoculation. Average tiller number/pot = 18.

1.8, and 2 × 2 mm, were inoculated at 1/leaf blade. Sclerotia produced on PDA, sizes 0.7 × 0.7, 1 × 1, 1.5 × 1.5, and 2 × 2 mm, were inoculated at 1 to 5/pot of seedlings. Lesions induced were counted and measured.

Sclerotia recovered from soil were 1 to 3 mm in size. The distribution frequency were 2.18% size 2 × 2 mm (or bigger), 12.18% 1.8 × 1.8 mm, 26.73% 1.5 × 1.5 mm, and 58.91% 1 × 1 mm.

Sclerotia size had a significant effect on infectivity. On detached rice leaves, average lesion number increased from

1.2 to 5.1 and average lesion size from 9 × 4 to 19 × 5.6 mm as sclerotia size increased from 1 × 1 to 2 × 2 mm (Table 1). On seedlings in pots, average lesion number increased from 0 to 31.6 and lesion length from 0 to 23.7 mm, as sclerotia size increased from 0.7 × 0.7 to 2 × 2 mm and sclerotia numbers from 1 to 5 (Table 2). □

Time of spraying to control sheath rot (ShR)

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We studied the effective time for fungicide application to control rice ShR in the greenhouse in two trials, five replications each.

The pathogen *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada was multiplied in rice grain

Table 1. ShR development after fungicide sprays. TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	ShR intensity at given days after treatment		
	5 d	10 d	15 d
Carbendazim 0.1%	0	3.7	6.3
Captafol 0.125%	0	0	6.3
Thiophanate methyl 0.1%	2.3	7.0	7.7
Carboxin 0.2%	3.7	6.3	7.7
Tridemorph 0.1%	3.0	7.0	7.7
Mancozeb 0.25%	2.3	7.0	8.3
Pyroquilon 0.1%	3.0	6.3	7.7
Iprodione 0.1%	3.7	6.3	7.7
Validamycin 0.1%	3.5	7.0	7.1
Kasugamycin 0.1%	3.7	6.3	7.0
Check	3.7	7.7	8.3
CD	1.2	1.5	ns ^a

^aNonsignificant.